

Can Secukinumab and Ustekinumab be useful in the treatment of Multiple Sclerosis?

Domina Petric

The most common immune-mediated inflammatory demyelinating disease of the central nervous system is multiple sclerosis (1).

Multiple sclerosis is categorized into 4 distinct types, primarily based on its clinical course, which are characterized by increasing severity: (a) Relapsing/remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS), the most common form, affecting 85% of all MS patients which involves relapses followed by remission; (b) secondary progressive multiple sclerosis (SPMS), which develops over time following diagnosis of RRMS; (c) primary progressive multiple sclerosis (PPMS) affecting 8-10% of patients, noted as gradual continuous neurologic deterioration; and (d) progressive relapsing multiple sclerosis (PRMS) the least common form (<5%), which is similar to PPMS but with overlapping relapses (2-4).

The autoimmune hypothesis of MS is well established. Myelin antigen-specific CD4+ T cells become activated in the peripheral immune compartment, cross the blood-brain barrier and trigger the disease (5).

Th17 cells play a crucial role in the pathogenesis of MS in both mice and humans by inducing an inflammatory milieu. In fact, IL-17A is present at high levels in CNS lesions, cerebrospinal fluid and in the serum of patients with MS (6). IL-23 is important for the differentiation of a subset of IL-17 producing T helper cells. Since naive T cells do not express the IL-23 receptor, IL-23 was refuted as an initial differentiation factor of Th17 cells. Rather the combination of TGF- β plus IL-6 or IL-21 were identified as differentiation factors of Th17 cells in mouse and man (7-11). However, IL-23 is still required as growth and maturation factor of pathogenic Th17 cells in vitro and in vivo (12).

Th17 cells express high levels of CCR6 which binds to the ligand CCL20 on vascular endothelial cells, enabling their entry through the blood brain barrier where they secrete pro-

inflammatory cytokines including IL-17A. In addition, IL-17 interferes with the remyelination process (6).

Based on the above mentioned findings it can be concluded that IL-17A and IL-23 are potential therapeutic targets in multiple sclerosis.

The proof-of-concept study published in 2016 provided the first evidence that blocking IL-17A with an antibody (secukinumab) may reduce MRI lesion activity in MS, but authors concluded that further studies are needed to confirm this finding and determine the magnitude of effect (13). Cortese and coworkers reported the clinical cases of two patients affected by a CNS demyelinating disease and ankylosing spondylitis who were successfully treated with secukinumab (14). Secukinumab may be an optimizing, feasible and cost-benefit therapeutic approach for patients with concurrence of multiple sclerosis and other rheumatologic diseases reducing, thereby, overexposure to other biological treatments as well as the incidence of adverse effects (15).

Ustekinumab (monoclonal antibody directed against interleukins IL-12 and IL-23) was tested in multiple sclerosis double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized, dose-ranging study. It was generally well tolerated but did not show efficacy in reducing the cumulative number of gadolinium-enhancing T1- weighted lesions in multiple sclerosis (16). Possible reasons for ustekinumab failure in MS are: (a) the drug's inability to cross the blood brain barrier, (b) the drug is effective in early stages of the disease, so patients with advanced disease did not respond, (c) alternative MS-causing pathways were undisrupted and/or interleukin 12/23 not critical to MS (17, 18). Chang and coworkers reported two patients with multiple sclerosis and comorbid psoriasis successfully treated with ustekinumab without progression of their multiple sclerosis (19).

If the problem with ustekinumab is in its inability to cross the blood brain barrier, as it is a large molecule drug with molecular weight of 148,600 Da, it could be reengineered with molecular Trojan horse delivery systems to access receptor-mediated transport systems within the blood-brain barrier. If the problem is that ustekinumab is effective only in early stages of the disease, then it is crucial to test it only on patients in early stages of multiple sclerosis. If IL-12/IL-23 is not critical to MS, then ustekinumab is not a drug of interest for multiple sclerosis.

To conclude, both secukinumab and ustekinumab could be useful in the treatment of multiple sclerosis, but more research is mandatory.

REFERENCES

1. Olek MJ, Mowry E. Pathogenesis and epidemiology of multiple sclerosis. Gonzales-Scarano F, ed. UpToDate. Waltham, MA: UpToDate Inc. <https://www.uptodate.com> (Accessed on April 10, 2021.)
2. Katsara M, Matsoukas J, Deraos G, Apostolopoulos V. Towards immunotherapeutic drugs and vaccines against multiple sclerosis. *Acta Biochim Biophys Sin (Shanghai)*. 2008;40(7):636-42.
3. Lublin FD, Reingold SC. Defining the clinical course of multiple sclerosis: results of an international survey. National Multiple Sclerosis Society (USA) Advisory Committee on Clinical Trials of New Agents in Multiple Sclerosis. *Neurology*. 1996 Apr;46(4):907-11.
4. Eckstein C, Bhatti MT. Currently approved and emerging oral therapies in multiple sclerosis: An update for the ophthalmologist. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 2016;61(3):318-32.
5. Korn T. Pathophysiology of multiple sclerosis. *J Neurol*, 2008;255(6):2-6.
6. Volpe E, Battistini L, Borsellino G. Advances in T Helper 17 Cell Biology: Pathogenic Role and Potential Therapy in Multiple Sclerosis. *Mediators Inflamm*. 2015;2015:475158.
7. Bettelli E, Carrier Y, Gao W, et al. Reciprocal developmental pathways for the generation of pathogenic effector TH17 and regulatory T cells. *Nature*. 2006;441(7090):235-8.
8. Korn T, Bettelli E, Gao W, et al. IL-21 initiates an alternative pathway to induce proinflammatory T(H)17 cells. *Nature*. 2007;448(7152):484-487.
9. Manel N, Unutmaz D, Littman DR. The differentiation of human T(H)-17 cells requires transforming growth factor-beta and induction of the nuclear receptor RORgamma. *Nat Immunol*. 2008;9(6):641-9.
10. Veldhoen M, Hocking RJ, Atkins CJ, et al. TGF-beta in the context of an inflammatory cytokine milieu supports de novo differentiation of IL-17-producing T cells. *Immunity*, 2006;24:179-189,
11. Yang L, Anderson DE, Baecher-Allan C, et al. IL-21 and TGF-beta are required for differentiation of human T(H)17 cells. *Nature*. 2008;454(7202):350-2.

12. McGeachy MJ, Bak-Jensen KS, Chen Y, et al. TGF-beta and IL-6 drive the production of IL-17 and IL-10 by T cells and restrain T(H)-17 cell-mediated pathology. *Nat Immunol.* 2007;8(12):1390-7.
13. Havrdová E, Belova A, Goloborodko A, et al. Activity of secukinumab, an anti-IL-17A antibody, on brain lesions in RRMS: results from a randomized, proof-of-concept study. *J Neurol.* 2016;263(7):1287-95.
14. Cortese A, Lucchetti R, Altobelli A, et al. Secukinumab may be a valid treatment option in patients with CNS demyelination and concurrent ankylosing spondylitis: Report of two clinical cases. *Mult. Scler. Relat. Disord.* 2019;35:193-195.
15. Cedeño RR. Secukinumab in Relapsing Multiple Sclerosis: experience in two cases with concomitant ankylosing spondylitis. *ECTRIMS Online Library.* 2017;200354.
16. Segal BM, Constantinescu CS, Raychaudhuri A, et al. Repeated subcutaneous injections of IL12/23 p40 neutralising antibody, ustekinumab, in patients with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis: a phase II, double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomised, dose-ranging study. *Lancet Neurol.* 2008;7(9):796-804.
17. Cingoz O. Ustekinumab. *MAbs.* 2009;1(3):216-21.
18. Longbrake EE, Racke MK. Why did IL-12/IL-23 antibody therapy fail in multiple sclerosis? *Expert Rev Neurother.* 2009;9(3):319-21.
19. Chang S, Chambers CJ, Liu FT, Armstrong AW. Successful treatment of psoriasis with ustekinumab in patients with multiple sclerosis. *Dermatol Online J.* 2015;21(7):13030/qt3bs971cr. PMID: 26436967.